

Evaluation of effective parameters on chemical reactions in the electrocells of Neka power station hypochlorite plant

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The optimum operating condition of chlorine production plant, in Neka power plant, has been examined. The effective parameters in the chlorine production have been studied. The stability of electrocells for a period of 120 h of operation for chlorine production is considered. The chlorine concentration drops from 2.45 to 2.15 g/l after six days of operation. The optimum operating conditions for the electrocells are evaluated. Acid wash, has often been used to remove the scale formed on the anode surface. Dimensionally stable anodes are applied in a series of electrocells for the production of required active chlorine concentration.

The electrolysis of sodium chloride solution for production of chlorine solution is one of the techniques in electrochemical industries. Gaseous chlorine in sodium hydroxide solution is the product of electrolysis of the salt solution. The chloralkali technology may involve several kinds of electrocell design. Mercury cells for production of chlorine is an out-dated method because of the environmental pollution¹. The diaphragm type chloralkali cells are the major electrocells used in US and Canada². More than 73% of chlorine is produced by diaphragm cells³. In modern cells, a vertical diaphragm separates the electrolyte into anolyte and catholyte. Purified brine enters into the anode compartments and a bulk flow of the solution goes through the diaphragm into cathode chambers. Direct current decomposes the salt in the brine to chlorine at the anode and hydroxyl ions (sodium hydroxide) plus hydrogen at the cathode. Concentrated sodium chloride solution (about 25%) is used in the electrocells. Oxygen, chlorine and chlorine oxides are liberated at the anode. Electrocells with graphite anode, in presence of oxygen, may produce carbon dioxide. Because of the graphite loss, the gap between anode and cathode will increase its inter-electrode resistance during the cell operation. As pH of the brine solution increases (pH above 7) the consumption of graphite dramatically increases⁴. For large - scale production, because of the graphite anode instability, it has been rapidly replaced by a newly found cell, using metal coated by other metal oxides as dimensionally stable anode (DSA). The anode consists of valuable metal, generally titanium, coated with crystal form of the metal oxides such as ruthenium oxide. Other types of metal coating may be used, either platinum or platinum/iridium alloy. The DSA can be used at low salt concentrations; it has high current

efficiency and long durability (lifetime 2–3 years)⁵. The electrode reaction of ionized brine solution with application of direct current results the following electrochemical reactions :

The third type of electrocells are chlorate cells with no separator barrier between anodic and cathodic products. In the electrochemical reaction process, the factors involved with the implementation of direct current across the cell are as follows : (i) reversible decomposition of brine solution, (ii) over potential at the electrodes, (iii) voltage drops in the electrolyte, (iv) voltage losses in the busbars and electrical conductors and (v) operating current density of the cells. Other factors such as temperature, salt concentration in the brine solution, electrolyte flow rate and pH would be effected on the operating condition. The noble anode of metal oxide coating on titanium was introduced in early 1970s. The advantages of DSA are discussed in the literature⁶. The DSA are usually used in this type of electrocells for production of low chlorine concentration. The raw material is salt solution free of heavy metals plus magnesium and calcium ions. These impurities may form scale on the electrode and short-circuit of electrodes will create hazardous problem for this type of electrocells.

The purpose of chlorine production plant in Neka Power Station, North of Iran, is chlorination of cooling water in the condensers. Chlorine solution is produced using sea water plus additional sodium chloride as a raw material for the electrocells. Because of the impurities of

sea water, several major problems associated with Neka chlorine production plant, may cause serious threat to the biggest and modern power plant in the Middle East region. Scale deposition causes electric short-circuiting phenomena, passivates anodes and increases cell resistance. The severe scale-deposit may force to shut down the plant for acid wash and replacement of burned electrodes.

Results and Discussion

The production of chlorine from Neka Power Station hypochlorite generation plant (Fig. 1) was observed for a period of 6 months in hot season. All effective parameters on electrocells were measured. The most important parameters examined were brine solution flow rate or retention time, DC current, DC voltage, active chlorine

of $37 \text{ m}^2 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The brine solution flow rate was varied from 33 to $48 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ keeping other set points such as DC voltage (122 V), DC current (2500 A), brine concentration (25.5 g dm^{-3}) fixed. Maximum daily chlorine production of 2238 kg was obtained with brine solution flow rate of $37 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$. Fig. 3 shows active chlorine concentration and daily production rate of chlorine vs brine solution flow rate. As the retention time in the electrocells decreases or the brine solution flow rate increases, the concentration of active chlorine is decreased from 2.7 to 1.9 g dm^{-3} . The flow rate of brine solution may have positive effect on daily production rate. The increase of the flow rate of brine solution by 41% also caused the daily rate of chlorine production increase by 4.8% . Plug flow cell arrangements are recom-

Fig. 1. Two sets of Neka's Power Station electrocells in parallel and series for brine solution

concentration, salt concentration, power consumption, electrocells in series, stability of cells and chlorine concentration during operation. It was observed that as the concentration of salt solution increases the concentration of active chlorine is increased and the voltage decreased. It shows that 25.5 g dm^{-3} salt concentration with 122 V would be the desired operating conditions. Fig. 2 shows that the active chlorine concentration and DC voltage are proportional to DC current. The DC current 2500 A , yields higher chlorine concentration with brine solution flow rate

mended in chloralkali industries because of low energy consumption. A linear increase in power consumption with respect to DC current was observed. Since high concentration of chlorine was demanded for the need of the power plant, therefore 2500 A , was selected. Fig. 4 shows the stability of the cells for period of 120 h ; the chlorine concentration was 2.48 g dm^{-3} in the starting the unit, the concentration gradually decreased to 2.2 g dm^{-3} at the end of the period. The chlorine concentration drop was caused by Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} ions scale deposition in the electrocells.

Fig. 2. Plots of DC current vs active chlorine and voltage of electrocells at different flow rates of brine solution

Fig. 3. Plots of brine solution flow rate vs chlorine production at 122 V DC current 2500 A and brine concn 25.5 g dm⁻³

Fig. 4. Stability of Neka's electrocells for chlorine production

Fig. 5. Plots of chlorine concentration profiles vs DC current of electrocells

Fig. 6. Plots of chlorine concentrations vs number of electrocells

There are two basic models for cells arrangements plug flow electrochemical reactor (PFER) and stirred tank flow electrochemical reactor (CSTER) The brine solution (electrolyte) flows through parallel to the electrodes at constant flow rate with fixed current density which is applied in normal direction of electrolyte flow The behavior of flow in the electrocells in CSTER shifted towards PFER as the cells are in series Fig 5 represents a mathematical model as DC current is dependent on chlorine concentration As the current changed from 1000 to 2500 A, the active chlorine concentration increased from 1 to 2.5 g dm⁻³ The rate of electrochemical reaction is directly proportional to the cell current density The rate equation in terms of current density and active chlorine concentration for the electrocells is

$$\frac{i}{nf} = K C_{Cl_2}^m \quad (4)$$

where K is the rate constant, m and nf are constant parameters In order to define all the constants, it is required to obtain a logarithmic form of eqn (5),

$$\ln(i) = \ln(nf K) + m \ln(C_{Cl_2}) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{i}{nf} = 4.813 \times 10^{-3} * C_{Cl_2}^{1.107} \quad (6)$$

and the plot is shown in Fig 5 The slope of the line, m is equal to 1.107, intercept $\ln(nf K)$ equals to 6.84 and K is 4.813E-3 Substitution of all constants represents the appropriate rate equation which is useful for the design of a new set of electrocells (eqn 6)

Fig 6 shows active chlorine concentration in the 36 electrocells in series As the number of cell increases the concentration of chlorine is increased and in the last cell the concentration is maximized Fig 6 shows linear fit for all the experimental data The fitted data in the Figs 5 and 6 show that the experimental results are compatible with the theoretical discussion

Experimental

The product of hypochlorite plant was added to the sea water, used for cooling purpose, with active chlorine con-

centration of 1.3–2 ppm. Neka chlorine production plant consisted of 9 groups of cells, each group having 4 individual cells as a production unit. All 36 Sanilec cells were electrically connected in series. The cell arrangements were bipolar because of the simplicity of electrical wiring, but there might be more chance of current leakage. Brine solution and generated chlorine in the solution flow in to parallel and series of electrocells, where the anode of the first cell and the cathode of the last cell were connected to 18 rod-shape long bolts of 16 mm size, with DC current charge of 2500 A. Each cell consisted of perforated DSA anode, titanium coated with ruthenium oxide followed by a cathode made of hastelloy C plates. The electrodes with 3.5 mm air-gap teflon spacers, consisted of 12 anodes and 11 cathodes. The cells were made of polypropylene with transparent cover of methyl metacrylate. The electrodes ($92 \times 22.5 \times 2$ cm with 18 holes) were mounted in series in each cell. Cross-sectional area of the cell was 22.5×8.7 cm, with 0.15 m s^{-1} linear velocity and 6.5 s retention time. The total anode surface was 4.1 m^2 per cell. Cyclone separators for ventilation of hydrogen and other gases were also mounted after second and fifth groups of cells. The electrochemical reactors were set up in up-flow direction. The brine solution (sea water plus NaCl) was continuously fed to pass through every set of electrocells so that the concentration of chlorine reached the final required active chlorine concentration. Detailed diagram showing the flow of liquid, outlet of NaOH solution as well as chlorine solution given in Fig. 1.

The bleaching activities of the solution were analyzed

for free and active chlorine using a strong acid. A 10% KI solution was used. The iodine was titrated with 0.1 N thiosulfate solution. Other colorimetric method was also developed with 10% potassium chromate solution⁷. Data were collected from the stage of production plant. There were limitation for change of flow rates of the brine solution and salt concentration and also for DC current applied to the electrocells.

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